

World Refugee Day 2025: don't let national emergency measures become the new standard of EU asylum policy

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- Every year on June 20th, World Refugee Day raises awareness for the plight of refugees and internally displaced persons.
- In Europe, the situation of people in need of protection is getting more precarious - fundamental rights risk being eroded by emergency asylum policies of EU member states.
- A series of crises and Russia's invasion of Ukraine have led to security considerations dominating asylum policy.
- The revised EU asylum laws give this type of measures greater significance, potentially facilitating rather than reversing this development.
- This Policy Brief recommends that national emergency measures should be applied with utmost care – and not to become a new standard in terms of how to deal with asylum-related challenges in the EU.

World Refugee Day is observed every year on June 20th. Led by the United Nations, its purpose is to raise awareness of the plight of refugees and internally displaced persons who have been forced to flee their homes due to war, conflict, or individual persecution. The day also underscores the importance of the 1951 Geneva Convention and the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights—both of which affirm the right to seek protection from persecution in another country.

Yet, this very right is increasingly being undermined in Europe. Several EU member states have begun addressing asylum-related challenges through emergency measures. This trend has accelerated since the so-called 'migration crisis', which began in the summer of 2015. This Policy Brief tracks this

development and recommends against normalizing emergency regimes in terms of dealing with refugees and asylum seekers in Europe.

Hungary during the “migration crisis”

Hungary was the first EU member state to institutionalise national emergency regimes in response to the “migration crisis” of 2015 and 2016. When the numbers of migrants arriving from Turkey on Greek soil (and then moving further north) increased in 2015, Hungary was one of Europe’s key transit countries. Initially, the EU Commission planned to include Hungary in its ‘emergency relocation program’ for refugees within the EU. This would have made Hungary, along with Italy and Greece, one of only three countries from which refugees would be systematically relocated to other EU states. However, Hungarian Prime Minister Viktor Orbán rejected a pan-European approach and instead relied on national deterrence and emergency measures. A 175-kilometer-long border fence made of barbed wire and other barriers was constructed in the summer and fall of 2015, and special ‘transit zones’ were established at the Hungarian-Serbian border where migrants were detained indefinitely.

A political and legal conflict broke out between the European Commission and the Hungarian government. The Commission initiated numerous infringement proceedings against Hungary at the Court of Justice of the EU to force compliance with EU asylum regulations. Legally, Hungary lost many of the cases. In June 2024, the country was fined €200 million for violating EU asylum law. According to the ECJ, Hungary had ‘deliberately’ failed to implement EU asylum law and ignored previous rulings, which constituted an ‘unprecedented and extremely serious infringement of EU law.’ Politically, however, the Hungarian government maintained its restrictive asylum policy: in 2024, only 25 asylum applications were registered in Hungary, according to Eurostat.

New Crises, New Exceptions

Hungary is no longer the only EU country pursuing national go-it-alone asylum policies that often neglect EU legal obligations. The most decisive crisis contributing to the normalization of national emergency measures within the EU was the ‘crisis’ at the border between the EU and Belarus. Since summer 2021, Belarusian dictator Lukashenko has been deliberately bringing migrants into Belarus and, with the help of Belarusian security forces, facilitating their crossing into the EU. Lukashenko’s response was a reaction to sanctions imposed by the EU after Belarus’s fraudulent 2020 elections.

The EU interpreted these actions as an attempt by Belarus to exert political pressure on the EU via the migration issue. Poland and the Baltic states responded with drastic emergency measures such as border closures, suspension of asylum rights, and systematic pushbacks. The European Commission expressed understanding and refrained from taking legal action against these practices. This approach by the Commission contradicted the views of many civil society actors, who saw Poland’s measures as a violation of European and international law and a legalization of pushbacks.

Within the EU, ongoing negotiations to reform the EU asylum system became increasingly dominated by security concerns and fears of the ‘instrumentalization’ of migration. The goal was also to align national emergency measures of Eastern European states with EU law.

The New EU Asylum Policy

The debate on how to deal with ‘emergencies’ was one of the most controversial aspects of negotiations over the European Pact on Migration and Asylum, which lasted from September 2020 to April 2024. No surprise – it was essentially about whether existing EU law could be disregarded in times of crisis and exceptional circumstances. Belarus’s tactics – and soon after, Russia’s invasion of Ukraine – led to a fundamental shift in the EU’s perception of its geopolitical environment.

A security- and control-oriented view of asylum gained increasing importance. According to own research interviews with negotiators, the Commission was ‘under massive pressure to legally enshrine exceptions to the principle of non-refoulement’. These exceptions and other controversial practices at the EU’s external borders would likely pose fewer legal issues if emergency measures played a more prominent role in EU law.

The regulation on ‘crisis situations and force majeure in the field of migration and asylum’ was adopted in May 2024 and now defines how member states can respond to emergencies. Such emergencies can include mass influxes of migrants, situations of instrumentalization, or ‘unusual and foreseeable events’. Once approved by the EU, affected states can apply exceptions to the relevant asylum procedure rules and demand solidarity measures from other EU member states.

The rules on crisis situations and force majeure are highly controversial. The same applies to other aspects of the pact, including expanded options for detaining asylum seekers and the growing shift of asylum procedures and protection to third countries. Shortly before the European Parliament voted on the legislative package, a group of 161 civil society organizations urged lawmakers to vote against it, arguing it would have ‘devastating effects on the right to international protection’ in the EU. However, the Parliament did not follow this appeal and adopted the pact together with the EU Council in May 2024. It will come into force in mid-2026.

The Future of EU Asylum Policy

Security considerations have fundamentally changed EU asylum policy. National emergency measures are maintained and increasingly institutionalized. The new EU Pact on Migration and Asylum does not oppose this development – it potentially even facilitates it.

The new scope of action that member states are carving out is already evident: In February 2025, the Polish parliament passed a bill allowing the suspension of asylum law if migration is used as a political weapon against the country. Given the aggressive foreign policy of Russia and Belarus, it is likely that Poland is planning these regulations for the long term and will effectively suspend asylum law at its external border with these countries. Other examples include national emergency measures effectively preventing migrants from asking asylum in border areas by the Baltic states or a Finnish law aimed at countering the instrumentalization of migration. Since becoming chancellor, the German government under Merz has made the direct turning away of asylum seekers at the country’s border into a priority and a formal policy. Austria’s new government has also agreed to ‘implement and further develop the Common European Asylum System with the goal of reducing domestic asylum applications to zero and triggering the emergency clause in case of rising numbers’. It remains unclear how this goal aligns with the right to seek asylum and what kind of ‘increase’ in asylum applications would constitute an emergency.

In summary: As the world honors refugees on June 20th, we should remember that their situation is becoming increasingly precarious in Europe. Policymakers should avoid normalizing policies that, just a few years ago, were seen as extreme and exceptional. People in need deserve a fair and accessible asylum process in a Europe that takes pride in its human rights traditions—values it rightly celebrates each year.

The views expressed in this publication are solely those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the Brussels Interdisciplinary Research Centre on Migration and Minorities or the Vrije Universiteit Brussel.

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